

Toward an independent reconstruction of the expansion history of the Universe

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The current tensions in cosmology, in particular the emerging discrepancy between the Hubble constant H_0 measured in the local universe with type-Ia supernovae and the one inferred from the CMB by assuming a Λ CDM model, require a deep understanding of the involved systematics and/or new physics, as well as the study of new and independent cosmological probes to better understand the expansion history of the Universe [1, 2].

In this context, *cosmic chronometers* (CC) have proven to be very promising probes to obtain *direct* measurements of the Hubble parameter $H(z)$ up to $z \sim 2$. The method, firstly introduced by Jimenez [3], consists in using massive and passive galaxies as tracers of the aging of the universe dt_U as a function of z under the minimal assumption of a FLRW metric, $H(z) = -(1+z)^{-1} dz/dt_U$. Provided that an accurate selection of CCs is performed, their aging dt can take the place of dt_U in the equation above. This method does not depend on the assumption of a specific cosmological model (e.g., Λ CDM), relies on differential – not absolute – age estimates, and makes use of a class of galaxies that is relatively simpler to model. However, accurate measurements require deep spectroscopic observations to break internal degeneracies between stellar population parameters (e.g., age and chemical content; for an updated review see [2]).

Cosmic chronometers in the LEGA-C survey

The Large Early Galaxy Census Astrophysics (LEGA-C, ESO programs 194.A-2005, 1100.A-0949) in an ESO public spectroscopic survey carried out at VLT/VIMOS targeting ~ 3000 K_s -band-selected galaxies at $0.6 < z < 1$ with typical continuum $S/N \sim 17$ and spectral resolution of $R \sim 3500$.

In Borghi [5], we select 350 cosmic chronometers in LEGA-C by crossing multiple observational criteria to maximize the purity of the sample: photometric $NUVrJ$ selection, spectroscopic $EW[OII]$ cut, and visual inspection of OII and OIII regions to further reduce galaxies with potential residual or recent star formation. With these criteria we obtain galaxies with a typical stellar velocity dispersion $\sigma_* \sim 206$ km s^{-1} , stellar mass $\log M_*/M_\odot \sim 11$, and specific star formation rates $\log sSFR/\text{yr} \sim -12$, typical of very massive and passive systems at this redshift.

We also study the H/K , a new diagnostic based on the Ca II H and K features measured as Lick indices. In passive systems, K is deeper than H, i.e. $H/K < 1$, but even the presence of a small fraction ($< 5\%$) of young (< 1 Gyr) stars, can invert the ratio. This is because A- and B-type stars have a strong $H\epsilon$ Balmer absorption line which overlaps the Ca II H line. In our passive

sample we measure, $\langle H/K \rangle = 0.96 \pm 0.08(1\sigma)$, which is an independent confirmation that our sample of cosmic chronometers is compatible with no or negligible star forming contaminants (for more details see Borghi [5]).

Figure 1: *Upper panel:* age–redshift relation for cosmic chronometers selected in the LEGA-C survey (gray points) binned to higher (red) and lower (blue) σ_* regimes. *Lower panel:* $H(z)$ measurement (violet star) with statistical (inner error bar) and total (outer error bar) uncertainties. Black points are literature data (see [2]). Figure from [7].

Analysis of the stellar populations properties

To better understand the physical properties (in particular the age) of the selected CCs, we measure informative spectral features (Lick indices) on each galaxy’s spectrum using `PyLick` (available at <https://gitlab.com/mmoresco/pylick>). An optimized set of indices is compared to the Thomas [6] simple stellar population models to constrain the mean age, $[Z/H]$, and $[\alpha/H]$. Extra care has been taken not to introduce cosmological assumptions which would invalidate the subsequent analysis. In particular, we do not set cosmological upper priors on the maximum allowed age.

We find that the parameter space covered by the CCs at $z \sim 0.7$ is comparable to the one of the local massive early type galaxies, with positive trends in stellar velocity dispersion, confirming the mass-downsizing scenario (i.e., more massive galaxies evolved earlier and faster). Within $0.6 < z < 0.9$ we observe no significant $[Z/H]$ and $[\alpha/H]$ evolution (typical values are $\langle [Z/H] \rangle = 0.08 \pm 0.18$ and $\langle [\alpha/Fe] \rangle = 0.13 \pm 0.11$), but a visible $age(z)$ trend (Figure 1, *upper panel*).

A new $H(z)$ measurement

In Borghi [7], we analyze the cosmological implications and, by applying the cosmic chronometer method, we obtain a new $H(z)$ measurement. We bin the LEGA-C CCs into two σ_* regimes (with a threshold of 215 km/s) and four z bins. This allows us to trace the underlying cosmological aging with sufficient resolution, while minimizing the scatter due to individual galaxies' formation pathways. We find two parallel median $\text{age}(z)$ relations with a difference of $\Delta \text{age} \approx 0.5$ Gyr that can be interpreted as a delay in formation time, with earlier formation epochs for more massive galaxies (Figure 1, *upper panel*). By measuring $\Delta z/\Delta \text{age}$ between each two non-consecutive bins, we derive four $H(z)$ measurements, that we average obtaining, $H(z) = 98.8 \pm 24.8$ (*stat*).

What are the main sources of systematic uncertainties? Previous efforts by Moresco [9] have demonstrated that the choice of the stellar population model plays a major role in the overall systematics of the CC approach, with an average contribution of about 7% on the final $H(z)$ value. We repeat the full analysis by changing: the assumed stellar population model and prescriptions, the choice of the Lick indices combination, and the binning method, obtaining a final value of $H(z) = 98.8 \pm 33.6$ (*stat + syst*) (Figure 1, *lower panel*). This is the first time the CC approach is applied with the Lick indices method, demonstrating that with high quality spectroscopy it is possible not only to study the properties of individual galaxies, but also to constrain their underlying cosmology.

Recently, Jiao [8] extended this work by using the full-spectrum fitting approach. Despite the completely different method, stellar population synthesis models and prescription (e.g. extended star formation history), the final $H(z)$ values are consistent within 0.2σ .

Future perspectives

A dedicated observing program targeting cosmic chronometers and a meticulous and detailed improvement of stellar population synthesis models, are the ideal pathways to reach the precision of other standard cosmological probes. In the near future, the combination of a BOSS-like and a EUCLID-like survey would already significantly improve our knowledge on $H(z)$ (Figure 2).

Already today, gravitational waves (GW) can provide an independent $H(z)$ hook at $z = 0$ for CCs. In fact, the GW signal from a compact binary coalescence is a direct tracer of its luminosity distance d_L [4], requiring no further

calibration other than the general relativity (unlike e.g., supernovae). By complementing this information with a z measurement (e.g., from an electromagnetic counterpart) or a statistical inference based on the distribution of potential hosts, it is therefore possible to obtain a local measurement of $H_0 \approx cz/d_L + \mathcal{O}(z^2)$. Moreover, with third generation GW detectors and upgrades of the existing ones it will be possible to study $d_L(z)$ and then infer the expansion history at higher redshift (Figure 2).

In conclusion, the synergy between cosmic chronometers and gravitational waves has a high potential to pave the way toward an independent reconstruction of the expansion history of the Universe.

Figure 2: Current and future constraints to the cosmic expansion history $H(z)$ using cosmic chronometers (CC; blue, see [2]) and gravitational wave events as standard sirens (SS; gold, see [10]).

References

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